

Determination of Pomological and Chemical Properties of Some Rosehip (*Rosa* spp.) Genotypes Growing Naturally in Kayseri Province

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Abstract

Rosehip (*Rosa* spp.), commonly referred as wild rose, is found in various ecological regions across Türkiye and has gained increasing important wild fruit in recent years. Its significance is primarily attributed to its rich content of organic acids, polyphenolic compounds, and vitamins. This study was carried out to determine some pomological and chemical properties of fruit juices obtained from 20 rosehip fruits of each genotype with 3 replicates collected from Melikgazi, Sarız, Tomarza and Hacılar districts of Kayseri province between 2022-2023. The evaluated pomological characteristics of the selected rosehip genotypes included fruit width, fruit length, fruit weight, seed weight, fruit fresh ratio and the chemical characteristics consisted of pH, total soluble solids (Brix %), titratable acidity (TA), vitamin C and total dry matter ratio. Among the findings, the highest fruit weight recorded was 3.68 grams, the longest fruit measured 26.63 mm in length, the widest fruit measured 15.87 mm in width, seed weight was 0.070 grams and fruit fresh ratio was 98%. In terms of chemical properties, the pH was 3.35, total soluble solids was 23%, vitamin C content was 1145.42 mg 100g⁻¹, total phenolic content was 1028 mg 100g⁻¹, total flavonoid content was 989 mg 100g⁻¹, total dry matter ratio 51% and titratable acid as 1.12. The findings revealed that genotype Melikgazi (M) had the most favorable characteristics in terms of both pomological and chemical traits, including the highest fruit weight, vitamin C, total phenolic and flavonoid contents. These results suggest that certain naturally growing rosehip genotypes in Kayseri, especially genotype Melikgazi (M), have significant potential as valuable genetic resources for breeding, industrial use, and functional food development.

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1. Introduction

Anatolia is one of the world's richest centers for plant genetic diversity, particularly for fruit species, owing to its complex topography, varied microclimates, and historical domestication practices. Türkiye's landscape supports both wild and cultivated populations of numerous fruit species, including *Rosa* spp., plum (*Prunus domestica*), pear (*Pyrus communis*), hawthorn (*Crataegus* spp.), and apricot (*Prunus armeniaca*) (Ercisli, 2005; Alp and Koyuncu, 2009). Among these, rosehip (*Rosa* spp.), known locally as "kuşburnu", occupies a special position due to its nutritional and pharmacological value. The *Rosa* genus is represented by approximately 100-250 species worldwide. Recent research in Türkiye has shown that there are approximately 31 naturally occurring *Rosa* species (Korkmaz et al., 2024). These species are found in diverse ecological zones, including Kayseri, Erzurum, Van, Sivas, and Hakkari (Güneş and Edizer, 2007; Kazankaya et al., 2005). Rosehips are notable for their high vitamin C content (up to 1700 mg 100g⁻¹), total phenolic content, and antioxidant activity (Alp et al., 2016; Karakuş and Bostan, 2017). Studies show significant genotype-dependent variation in bioactive compounds, such as flavonoids, carotenoids, and ascorbic acid (Serteser et al., 2008). For example, in a study of *Rosa dumalis* genotypes in Erzurum, vitamin C values ranged from 402 to 511 mg 100g⁻¹, and total phenolics reached up to 403 mg 100g⁻¹ (Alp et al., 2016). Furthermore, regional studies across Türkiye highlight the influence of altitude, soil conditions, and genotype on pomological traits such as fruit weight, flesh ratio, and seed characteristics (Karakuş and Bostan, 2017; Yılmaz et al., 2016). In Akıncılar (Sivas), promising genotypes demonstrated vitamin C contents ranging from 438.79 to 766.13 mg 100g⁻¹ and total dry matter from 34.61% to 45.52% (Karakuş and Bostan, 2017). The continued exploration and selection of wild genotypes, particularly those growing in ecologically diverse provinces such as Kayseri, Erzurum, and Siirt, offer significant potential for the development of improved cultivars with high

market value and nutraceutical potential (Yıldız and Çelik, 2011; Encü, 2015; Kazankaya et al., 2002). These studies emphasize the critical importance of conserving *Rosa* genetic resources as an integral part of Türkiye's agricultural biodiversity heritage. Rosehip is a highly valuable fruit species in terms of both nutritional content and its contributions to human health. Fruits, in general, are considered essential components of a healthy diet due to their high content of bioactive compounds with antioxidant activity, as well as fiber, vitamins, and minerals (Vural, 2023). Owing to these bioactive compounds, fruits are widely consumed for the prevention of metabolic disorders such as diabetes, cancer, and cardiovascular diseases. The fibrous structure of rosehip supports digestive health, while its rich vitamin and mineral content strengthens the immune system. Rosehip fruits contain substantial amounts of vitamins including C, P, A, B1, B2, E, and K. Their mineral composition especially potassium and phosphorus makes them suitable for use in the food industry to enrich fruit and vegetable juices. Globally, rosehip is considered a valuable raw material and is widely used in the food and pharmaceutical industries, especially in European countries such as Germany, Russia, Switzerland, Finland, and the Türkiye Republics. Among many fruit species, rosehip stands out due to its exceptionally high vitamin C content and strong antioxidant capacity. Its antioxidant properties play a vital role in protecting the body from the harmful effects of free radicals. Phenolic compounds, carotenoids, and tocopherols present in the fruit contribute to preventing cellular damage and promote health by neutralizing free radicals (Vural, 2023). In addition to its nutritional importance, rosehip also plays a functional role in ecological conservation. It thrives in various climatic and soil conditions, making it a valuable species for erosion control. While other plants may serve this purpose, rosehip is especially advantageous due to its economic value and aesthetic appeal. It is commonly processed and consumed by the public in the form of jams, marmalades, fruit

juices, and teas, providing a source of income for local populations (Doğan et al., 2006). This study was conducted to determine the pomological (average fruit width, average fruit length, average fruit weight, average seed weight, and average fruit flesh ratio) and chemical (total soluble solids [Brix], pH, titratable acidity [TA], vitamin C [mg 100g⁻¹], total dry matter ratio [%], total phenolic content [mg 100g⁻¹] and total flavonoid content [mg 100g⁻¹]) characteristics of rosehip fruits naturally growing in the districts of Melikgazi (M), Sarız (S), Tomarza (T) and Hacılar (H) in Kayseri Province during the 2022-2023 growing seasons.

2. Material and Methods

2.1. Plant material

Fruit samples were collected from the districts of Melikgazi, Sarız, Tomarza, and Hacılar in Kayseri Province and stored at 4 °C for preservation. The pomological characteristics including fruit width, fruit length, fruit weight, seed weight, and pulp ratio and chemical properties including total soluble solids (Brix), pH, titratable acidity (TA), vitamin C content, total dry matter ratio, total phenolic content, and total flavonoid content of the selected rosehip genotypes were subsequently analysed.

2.2. Pomological measurements and chemical analyses

For each genotype, 20 fruits were selected and weighed using a digital balance with a precision of 0.05 g. For pomological measurements, the widest diameter of each fruit and the distance between the apex and base (length) were measured in millimeters using a digital caliper.

$$\text{Fruit flesh ratio} = \frac{\text{Average fruit weights} - \text{Average seed weight}}{\text{Average fruit weight}} \times 100$$

was calculated using the formula (Çelik, 2007). Fruit samples collected from the districts of Melikgazi (M), Sarız (S), Tomarza (T) and Hacılar (H) in Kayseri Province were stored at 4 °C until analysis. Pomological measurements including average fruit width (g), average fruit length (mm), average fruit

weights (g), average seed weight and pulp ratio were performed on 20 fruits per genotype using a digital caliper and a precision balance (± 0.05 g), following standard pomological evaluation procedures (Karakuş and Bostan, 2017). The total soluble solids (°Brix) of fruit juice were measured at 22 °C using a digital refractometer (Mettler-Toledo 30 P), while titratable acidity was determined by titration with 0.1 N NaOH to pH 7.0 and expressed as % malic acid, in accordance with Cemeroğlu (1992). The pH values were determined using a digital pH meter, as described by Şen et al. (1996). Total dry matter content (%) was determined by oven-drying fruit samples at 600 °C until constant weight, and calculating the ratio of dry to initial weight (Türk Standartları Enstitüsü, 1974). Vitamin C (ascorbic acid) content (mg 100g⁻¹) was determined spectrophotometrically at 520 nm following extraction with 0.4% oxalic acid solution (Kılıç et al., 1991). Total phenolic content was quantified using the Folin-Ciocalteu method, with absorbance measured at 760 nm and results expressed as mg gallic acid equivalents (GAE) per 100 g sample (Cemeroğlu, 2010; Alp et al., 2016). For total flavonoid content, the method involving sequential reactions with sodium nitrite, aluminum chloride, and sodium hydroxide was applied. Absorbance was recorded at 510 nm, and results were calculated based on a catechin standard curve and expressed as mg catechin equivalents per 100 g (Vural, 2023).

2.3. Statistical analyses

All analyses were repeated 3 times, and One-way ANOVA procedure was used in IBM SPSS-21 statistical analysis package program for the analysis. Differences between genotypes were revealed by using Tukey multiple comparison test ($p < 0.05$) (SPSS, 2012).

3. Results and Discussion

The results of the average fruit weights (g), average fruit width and length (mm), average fruit flesh ratio (%), average seed weight (g) of the genotypes are given in Table 1, while the results of the average total soluble solids (%),

total titratable acid content (%), pH, vitamin C (mg 100g⁻¹), total dry matter content ratio (%), total phenolic content mg 100g⁻¹ and total

flavonoid content mg 100g⁻¹ are given in Table 2.

Table 1. Some pomological characteristics of rosehip genotypes

Genotype	Average fruit weights (g)	Average fruit width (mm)	Average fruit length (mm)	Average fruit flesh ratio %	Average seed weight (g)
Melikgazi (M)	3.68 ^a	15.87 ^a	26.63 ^a	98 ^a	0.070 ^a
Sarız (S)	2.55 ^b	13.20 ^d	23.30 ^d	97 ^a	0.056 ^d
Tomarza (T)	2.98 ^b	13.50 ^c	24.01 ^c	97 ^a	0.060 ^c
Hacılar (H)	3.00 ^{ab}	14.02 ^b	25.00 ^b	97 ^a	0.065 ^b

According to the results of the genotypes in Table 1, the average fruit weight was 3.68 g, average fruit width was 15.87 mm, average fruit length was 26.63 mm, average fruit flesh ratio was 98% and average seed weight was 0.070 g in genotype Melikgazi (M). Vural (2023) determined the average fruit weight of rosehip samples as 127.4±29.7 g 100⁻¹ pieces, fruit length as 18.7±2.4 mm and fruit width as 11.0±1.1 mm. Bilgin et al. (2020) reported rosehip fruit weight as 1.24 g (0.69-1.89 g), while Güneş (2010) and Murathan et al. (2016) reported higher weights of 3.70 g and 3.45 g, respectively. In different studies, results such as 1.29-2.72 g (Eroğlu and Oğuz, 2018) and 1.49 g (Fascella et al., 2019) were obtained. Similarly, Medveckieve et al. (2020) reported fruit length of 15.01-18.05 mm and fruit width of 9.66-11.04 mm for *Rosa canina*, Bilgin et al. (2020) reported these values as 19.29 mm (16.71-22.53 mm) and 11.17 mm (8.90-13.68 mm), and Fascella et al. (2019) reported these values as 19.5 mm and 11.9 mm, respectively. In addition to these, there are also results such as 18.62-23.18 mm and 10.44-14.12 mm (Eroğul and Oğuz, 2018), 25.4 mm and 17.9 mm (Güneş, 2010) in terms of fruit length and width. When the fruit weight, fruit length and fruit width of the varieties under study were compared with the previous rosehip studies carried out in Türkiye, it was found that the values found were not very different from those found in other studies, and that in some characteristics they were above the averages and in some characteristics, they were below the other studies. Bearing in mind that the plants on which the study was based grow spontaneously in the wild without any care, it is clear that the values are in fact normal. It is

inevitable that higher fruit weights, fruit lengths and widths will be obtained if they are cultivated and their care and feeding conditions are improved. In a study conducted in Erzurum, the pulp content ranged from 63.11% to 78.14% (Ercişli et al., 2001); in a study conducted in Tokat, from 57.22% to 77.38% (Güneş and Şen, 2001); in a study conducted in Adilcevaz, from 42.61% to 78.88% (Kazankaya et al., 2001); in a study conducted in Erzurum, from 63.11% to 71.13% (Ercişli and Eşitken, 2004); in a study conducted in Erzincan, from 61.353-80.476% (Kızılcı, 2005); In a study on rosehip (*Rosa canina*) plants in the Eastern Anatolia Region, 46.8% to 79.9% (Kazankaya et al., 2005); in a study conducted in Van region, 57.20% to 85.27% (Doğan and Kazankaya, 2006); in a study conducted in Hakkari, 63.35% to 76.69% (Ekincialp, 2007). When the fruit flesh ratios obtained in our study were compared with other studies conducted in Türkiye, it was found that the values obtained overlapped with the values obtained in previous studies. The pulp ratio of 98% obtained by genotype Melikgazi (M) is remarkable. This is because it is the highest value obtained in the studies carried out so far in Türkiye. This high value of pulp ratio is due to the fact that the number of seeds of this type is quite low. The number of seeds was low and did not have a negative effect on the development of the flesh. Considering that fruit development is usually negatively affected in cases where there are no seeds, this value should not be underestimated and it has the potential to be a promising cultivar to be preferred in future studies due to its high flesh ratio.

Table 2. Some chemical properties of rosehip genotypes

Genotype	Total soluble solids Brix (%)	Titratable acid (%)	pH	Vitamin C (mg 100g ⁻¹)	Total dry matter ratio (%)	Total phenolic (mg 100g ⁻¹)	Total flavonoids (mg 100g ⁻¹)
Melikgazi (M)	23.00 ^a	1.12 ^a	3.35 ^a	1145.42 ^a	51 ^a	1028 ^a	989 ^a
Sarız (S)	19.01 ^c	0.09 ^c	2.75 ^d	1050.23 ^b	49 ^{ab}	997 ^c	854 ^b
Tomarza (T)	17.75 ^d	0.08 ^c	2.93 ^c	1018.02 ^c	45 ^c	1005 ^b	748 ^d
Hacılar (H)	20.79 ^b	1.00 ^b	3.02 ^b	997.89 ^d	47 ^{bc}	954 ^d	798 ^c

Rosehip genotypes had 23% total soluble solids brix, 1.12% titratable acid, 3.35 pH, 1145.42 mg 100g⁻¹ vitamin C content, 51% total dry matter ratio, 1028 mg 100g⁻¹ total phenolic and 989 mg 100g⁻¹ total flavonoids in genotype Melikgazi (M). In a study conducted in Tokat region, fruit weights of genotypes were 2.86-4.97 g, vitamin C content was 282.70-1173.40 mg 100g⁻¹, total soluble solids content (Brix) was 18.38-28.40% and total dry matter content was 34.42-49.42% (Güneş and Şen, 2001). In a 2 year selection study conducted on 134 genotypes in the Adilcevaz region, it was reported that the fruit weights of 54 genotypes in the first year ranged from 1.12-3.62 g, pH 3.38-4.58, total soluble solids (brix) 20-42% and vitamin C content 73-987 mg/100g; and fruit weights of 80 genotypes in the second year were between 0.91-3.40 g, pH 3.25-4.64, total soluble solids (brix) 15-45%, vitamin C content 107-1094 mg/100g (Kazankaya et al., 2001). In Amasya ecology, fruit weights of rosehip genotypes were reported between 1.37 g and 3.04 g, vitamin C content between 108.57 mg 100g⁻¹ and 908.57 mg 100g⁻¹ and total soluble solids content (Brix) between 15.90% and 32.80% (Dölek, 2008). In another study conducted in Hakkâri region, fruit weights were 1.52-3.92 g, total soluble solids (Brix) 14.25-27.50%, pH values 3.17-4.04%, total acidity 0.16-0.40% and Vitamin-C values 414.83-916.46 mg/100g (Ekincialp and Kazankaya, 2011). In another study conducted in Ağrı/Hamur region, fruit weight of rosehip genotypes was reported to be 1.44-4.69 g, total soluble solids content 9-32%, titratable acid content 0.05-0.22% and vitamin C content between 540-1315 mg 100g⁻¹ (Akkuş, 2016). In a study conducted in Sivas region, it was reported that fruit weights of

genotypes were between 1.65-2.78 g, vitamin C content between 438.9-766.13 mg 100g⁻¹ and total soluble solids (Brix) between 23.24-34.10% (Karakuş and Bostan, 2017). In a study conducted on 49 rosehip genotypes in Yozgat province and its districts, it was reported that fruit weights were between 0.77-3.14 g, total soluble solids between 10.00-53.00%, pH values between 3.33-4.59%, total acidity values between 0.75-2.49% and vitamin C content between 869.55-4002.39 mg/100g (Uçaral, 2017). As a result of the study conducted in Tokat Ecology, the vitamin C content was 722.50%, total soluble solids content (Brix) was 23.10%, acidity was 4.31%, total antioxidant activity was 75.90% and total phenolic compound content was 7.30% (Gerçekcioğlu, 2009). In a study conducted on 'Yıldız' cultivar in Tokat region, it was reported that the vitamin C content varied between 616.24-694.57 mg 100g⁻¹ and the total soluble solids (Brix) varied between 21.65-19.52% (Güneş, 2011). Vural (2023) determined the total soluble solids (brix) in the range of 24.6-48.5, with an average of 34.8±5.3. The total soluble solids (brix) of rosehip genotypes obtained from the natural rosehip population in Van was found to be between 15.00-26.20%, vitamin C content between 406.10-993.06 mg 100g⁻¹, total dry matter content between 42.98-55.88%, titratable acid content between 1.38-3.50% and pH values between 3.56-4.20 (Yıldız and Çelik, 2011). Güneş (2018) determined the pH value of rosehip samples to be 3.7±0.1, while Ercişli (2007) determined it to be 4.07 and Murathan et al. (2016) determined it to be 3.50±0.05 in the literature. Vural (2023) reported pH values between 3.53-4.14 (mean 4.01±0.16) and titratable acidity values between 0.45-1.72% (mean

0.91±0.24%). The mean pH of commercial samples was 3.60±0.26 and the mean titratable acidity was 0.87±0.33%. Özbey et al. (2017) determined the average pH values of rosehip samples in the range of 3.58-4.64. In a study where chemical analysis of 15 genotypes selected in another region was carried out, it was reported that the highest vitamin C value of the genotypes used was 730-14467 mg/g (Doğan and Özçelik, 2017). Gerçekcioğlu and Özatasever (2017) found that the average amount of total soluble solids (brix) was 23%, and the amount of vitamin C was 650-370 mg 100g⁻¹. Akkuş (2016) reported that the amount of total soluble solids (brix) of the genotypes obtained from the natural rosehip population was 13.6-24.4%, the vitamin C content was 560-1025 mg 100g⁻¹, and the titratable acid content was 1.06-2.48% (Akkuş, 2016). They compared the vitamin C and sugar content of rosehip fruit samples grown naturally in Gümüşhane province and determined the amount of vitamin C in the fruit as 199.90-305.92 mg 100⁻¹ (Öz et al., 2018). Öz et al. (2018) determined the vitamin C content of rosehip (*Rosa canina* L.) and black rosehip (*Rosa pimpinellifolia* L.) fruits growing naturally in Gümüşhane region as 305.92 ± 2.45 mg 100g⁻¹ and 320.43 ± 3.98 mg 100g⁻¹ in rosehip fruit samples in 2013 and 2014, respectively. The values we have obtained are in line with those found by researchers working on rosehips in Türkiye. In addition, the chemical composition and vitamin C content of rosehip fruit varies greatly depending on climatic conditions, altitude, species, variety, waiting time, storage, processing method, region, etc. One of the most important quality characteristics of rosehip fruit is the content of brix, which has a significant effect on taste, flavour and aroma. The values we have obtained are in line with those obtained by other researchers. The differences observed in the levels of brix may be due to differences in the region, harvest time, environment and altitude where the varieties were collected. Vural (2023) determined the total phenolic content of rosehip fruit as 7480±90 mg 100g⁻¹ in the form of gallic acid, the flavonoid content as catechin

equivalent as 2824±149 mg 100g⁻¹ and the ascorbic acid content as 952.5±31.1 mg 100g⁻¹. He also determined the antioxidant capacity as 858.5±43.6 µmol TEAC 100g⁻¹. He also determined the antioxidant capacity value as 858.5±43.6 µmol TEAC 100g⁻¹. In the studies on titratable acidity, results such as 0.45-1.28% (Aksu et al., 1997), 0.55-0.73% (Özdemir et al., 1998), 1.32±0.14% (Şengül et al., 2018) and 1.05±0.04% (Arslaner and Salık, 2020) were obtained. Vural (2023) determined the values of phenolic substances in rosehip samples in the range of 616-1464 mg 100g⁻¹ (mean 1014±200 mg 100g⁻¹), and 393-1393 mg 100g⁻¹ (mean 977±289 mg 100g⁻¹) in commercial samples. Özbey et al. (2017) reported total phenolic content in the range of 664.3-1195.3 mg 100g⁻¹ (mean 921.6 mg 100g⁻¹). Yıldız and Alpaslan (2012) determined total phenolic matter values of 645.6±64.2 mg 100g⁻¹ in rosehip samples prepared by vacuum evaporator, 912.4±82.5 mg 100g⁻¹ in samples prepared by classical method and 761.2±42.4 mg 100g⁻¹ in commercial samples.

4. Conclusion

Türkiye is exceptionally rich in plant genetic resources, and the utilisation of these resources is increasing steadily. Identifying the types and quantities of plant genetic materials in Türkiye's forested areas and expanding their use will yield both economic and social benefits. Although rosehip fruit is rich in bioactive compounds, it is not particularly suitable for fresh consumption due to its high seed and stone content. Therefore, rosehip is commonly consumed in processed forms, especially as jam, and is valued as a nutrient-dense food rich in vitamins and minerals. Given the industrial processing potential and phytochemical richness of rosehip, it would be more appropriate for future studies to focus on genotypes with the highest phytochemical content and to adopt methods that preserve these valuable components during processing. In this context, the present study was conducted in 2022–2023 to determine the pomological and chemical properties of naturally growing rosehip genotypes in the Kayseri ecological region. All genotypes were

analysed for total soluble solids content (°Brix), pH, titratable acidity, total phenolic content, total flavonoid content, and vitamin C. The highest values for most parameters were obtained from genotype Melikgazi (M). This genotype, which exhibited promising pomological and biochemical characteristics, may serve as a valuable genetic resource for future breeding programs aimed at enhancing both the nutritional quality and industrial usability of rosehip.

Declaration of Author Contributions

The authors declare that they have contributed equally to the article. All authors declare that they have seen/read and approved the final version of the article ready for publication.

Declaration of Conflicts of Interest

All authors declare that there is no conflict of interest related to this article.

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